

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Keynote of case letter

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist faced life-threatening conspiracy and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school since 2021-2022. He proposed 230,72,50,000 AUD (two hundred thirty crore seventy-two lakh and fifty thousand Australian dollar) to the government of Australia for his PhD compensation. The scholarly convincing of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist denoted and

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proposed as 'PhD compensation award of Australian government'. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President of Bangladesh; Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh government to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

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Keywords

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President of Bangladesh; Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Date 7 November 2024

Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin
President
Office of President
The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
Office of President, Bangabhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh
secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd
press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd
ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd
akmmonirul31@gmail.com

Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Economist
Chief Advisor
Office of Chief Advisor
The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
State Guest House Jamuna, Dhaka, Bangladesh
majumderali1950@gmail.com
musfiquldu33@gmail.com
psecy@cao.gov.bd
secretary@cao.gov.bd
seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd
lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

Let's shout and shout for a 'criminal free' world rather than 'weapon therapy', a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist.

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

sultanpmo1974@gmail.com

ddresearch@cao.gov.bd

jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd

May I seek income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Dear President and Chief Advisor,

Your Excellency for the peace of mankind

Your honour to ensure legal rights of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour to ensure legal safety of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour for the excellency of global leadership

Your honour for keeping a quality relation with the government of Australia

I would like to claim self-life-threatening conspiracy at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia. I, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist have been a victim in Australian PhD school. I am not happy to write this letter to the offices of 'president' and 'chief advisor'. But I would like to write for my lifelong survival and self-protection as a unit of human-being.

I got a valid passport of Bangladesh government, a valid student VISA of Australian government, a valid PhD scholarship of Australian government, and a valid 'study leave' letter from the Bangladesh government. I faced a life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Australia. The conspiracy was also continued, extended, and bypassed to Bangladesh in different ways. The victim tried and tried to protect from Australian criminal. I reported to the relevant authorities of Australian government, such as vice chancellor of RMIT University, Australian police, Australian education minister, Australian law minister, Australian prime minister, Australian ministry of home affairs, Australian high commissioner in Bangladesh, and relevant criminal investigation departments in Australia, etc. Accordingly, I also parallelly reported to the relevant authorities of Bangladesh government, such as vice chancellor

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of City University, chairman of university grant commission, foreign ministry of Bangladesh, education ministry of Bangladesh, Bangladesh high commissioner in Australia, and relevant criminal investigation departments, etc. Mr. Anthony Albanese, Australian Prime Minister; and Mr. Jason Clare, Australian Education Minister were assessing and assessing since 2 December 2023 (reference: MC23-103435, attached at the end of this letter) but they are taking so much time but I am waiting and waiting, but I have no food in my stomach to convince them long-term duration. I had not been got my salary of RMIT University since 6 July 2022, but I was reporting, informing and requesting to Australian government since 2021-2022. Therefore, I have been sacrificing my quality of lifestyle since 6 July 2022. Hence, I would like to seek income support as a valid citizen of Bangladesh government if I am eligible under my situation of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Australia. Presently, I am residing in Bangladesh at village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Presently I have no financial capability for going to Australian expensive court and/or international court and/or any legal support for my legal and ethical achievements. Australian government has no practice of legal insurance against RTP stipend scholarship. Moreover, I asked for a 'legal stipend' to face Australian court, but my request and begging were 100% denied and nullified by the relevant authorities of Australian government.

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Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

I proposed to the government of Australia to pay 230,72,50,000 AUD (two hundred thirty crore seventy-two lakh and fifty thousand Australian dollar) for my PhD compensation award for my scholarly convincing to the whole Australian government since 2021-2022 to still now. I proposed legal action of Australian home affairs for 8390000 Australian penalty unit (230,72,50,000 AUD) as 'PhD compensation award of Australian government'. The scholarly convincing of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain represented, requested, and proposed as a 'PhD compensation award of Australian government'. I asked for life-time income support and life-time

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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engranowar06@gmail.com

safety support from the Australian government through the proposed compensation amount. I am also a legal part of human being. I am feeling so much shame that I am personally unable to solve an international issue without the right support of Bangladesh government and Australian government. Finally, I am also writing to your office of 'president' and office of 'chief advisor' of Bangladesh government. What is my exact weak point? What should I do? Why should I write a letter to the president of Bangladesh government? Why should I write a letter to the chief advisor of Bangladesh government? Why should I seek support from the prime minister of Australian government? Why should I seek support from the education minister of Australian government? Professor Dr. Alec Cameron successfully showed zero responsibility from the office of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Australia. If the criminal is hacking the university, Professor Cameron should have a voice or the right action for the peace in PhD schooling. The student union of RMIT University was also silent and silent. Is it my crime to be 100% obedient to professor or an Australian university? An Australian professor can not make a hidden plan to kill a PhD student without the valid permission of an Australian court or the vice chancellor of RMIT University. Possibly Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye (e-mail: rajiv.padhye@rmit.edu.au Phone: +61399259124) planned and tried to kill me by his hidden technique of human practice and human intelligence under the administrative umbrella of RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia. Figure 1, if Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and his associates are practicing against Australian quality of research framework and/or peace in PhD schooling, may I propose the 'death penalty' of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye with the right PhD compensation to eliminate repeated occurrences for their long-term action against the peace in PhD schooling? Crime in PhD school should have zero tolerance all over the world. PhD student killing should be an offence as per Australian quality of research framework. As criminals are so much talent, as criminals are practicing so much power, may I seek the safety support of Australian government. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye not only tried to kill me, but he also threw and threw his administrative bullet to kill the quality of my PhD thesis when the quality is the key requirement of a PhD thesis. He also threw his administrative bullet like rain and rain in a PhD school. A professor should throw his/her administrative bullet to improve the quality of a PhD thesis to improve the quality of a PhD candidate. If I am 100% obedient to the discipline in the PhD school, why should the professor kill me? What was the necessity to kill Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist through the connection with St. Vincent's hospital in Melbourne through the connection with the emergency medical team? There is a huge scope of research and development for international criminal investigation for the peace in global PhD schooling. What was the PhD ordinance to kill a PhD student of RMIT University, Australia? We will not kill scientist,

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researcher, student, and professor through PhD ordinance. We will not kill scientist, researcher, student, and professor in the name of psychologist recommendation. We will not try to kill scientist, researcher, student, and professor without lawful reason. The victim is alive still now, but there has been no investigation of a life-threatening conspiracy in an Australian PhD school since 2021-2022, if the victim is supposed to die, what may happen? It would not be a matter of writing this letter to the office of 'president' and the office of 'chief advisor' of Bangladesh government. So, what is the exact situation of human rights in a PhD school? The world is progressing and progressing, but human rights are declining and declining. I am afraid that blood is flowing all over the world. We are only saying, citing and reciting the word of 'human rights'. The situation seems that the whole world has a lack of guardian. I had been trying, writing, and begging since 2021-2022. I was begging and begging to continue my PhD research at the location of 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, since 2022. It seems that no government is responsible, no organization is responsible if I can not invest money for the legal support, but I can not continue my writing and begging with an empty stomach when I have no income support in Bangladesh and Australia. In 2021-2022, the life-threatening history was officially notified to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University and the whole administrative concern of RMIT University, but I got an 'illegal gift letter' of 'PhD suspension' and 'psychologist recommendation' for one year duration on 6 July 2022. I also sincerely and obediently respected the office order of the RMIT University. The support and safety of the victim was nullified again and again. 'Psychologist recommendation' is also an unethical way of additional power implementation to a victim in addition to continuous life-threatening. The victim is failing and failing when the unethical power is winning and winning in a PhD school. Unethical power versus unethical PhD suspension versus criminals are winning and winning. Ethical versus moral principles are failing and failing in PhD school. The killing conspiracy and PhD research harassment was parallelly tried and sequenced as hospital connection in Melbourne-PhD suspension-psychologist recommendation-family connections-connections with Bangladeshi peoples in Bangladesh and Australia. I would like to seek the right funding to investigate my written report on behalf of Bangladesh government, on behalf of Australian government, on behalf of national and international human rights commission, on behalf of united nations, on behalf of relevant authorities all over the world. I would like to seek an ethical voice to investigate on behalf of Bangladesh government, on behalf of Australian government, on behalf of national and international human rights commissions all over the world, on behalf of united nations, on behalf of relevant authorities. On behalf of judicial ministries or judicial commissions, an ethical justice board of Bangladesh government, and an ethical justice board of Australian government may assess the written copy of incidence of victim for national and international proceedings for the global excellency. May I want legal funding with scholarly income support to Bangladesh government, Australian government, national and international human rights commissions all over

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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engranowar06@gmail.com

the world, united nations, and relevant authorities? This is not my personal issue; this is not an issue of Bangladesh government; this is not an issue of Australian government; it should be a global issue; this is necessity for the global peace of mankind; this is necessity for the global peace in PhD schooling all over the world. I am a tiny unit of human being, and nobody is hearing my voice, when I have no weapon, when I have no power, when I have no money, and possibly these are my related crimes. Let's eliminate the whole criminal from the PhD school all over the world. Let's eliminate the whole criminal all over the world; let's shout and shout for a 'criminal free' world rather than weapon therapy. I am also announcing the whole world for their legal and ethical support for the peace of mankind. PhD school is a global research centre. PhD school is a specialized teaching and learning centre. PhD school is a global practice centre of ethics and ethics. PhD school has no chance of a life-threatening conspiracy.

Figure 1, Hidden attempts, research, planned actions, intelligence activities, sincere, and deep concentrated duty of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye in PhD school to kill a PhD candidate at RMIT

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University, Melbourne, Australia. Possibly, these are not symptom of mental health disease of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye. There is also brief explanation in different links in different case letters for the assessment, understanding, and case reporting to relevant authorities of Australian government.

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Figure 1, Accordingly, I also continued and notified the brief of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school to the whole concern of Australian community under the Australian quality of research framework in Australia. The whole life-threatening conspiracy has already been briefly explained in the report on

“Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224211>

I also fulfilled the PhD requirement of RMIT University under the examination of first and second milestone examination of PhD degree under the congratulation of two separate PhD committee of RMIT University. But still now I didn’t get a certified copy of my PhD degree of RMIT University. A certificate of my PhD degree is my scholarly achievement. Nobody should cease my certified copy of my PhD degree at RMIT University. Nobody should cease my mark sheets of my PhD degree at RMIT University. I would like to show my printed copy of my ‘PhD certificate’ all over the world. I paid 100% for PhD course registration fees through RTP stipend scholarship. Hence, I paid 100% for PhD laboratory access, PhD library access and PhD supervisors at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Nobody should cease my scholarly achievement and scholarly practice at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Nobody should cease my PhD laboratory funded and paid by RTP stipend scholarship. Nobody should cease my scholarship money. I sincerely and sincerely, obediently and obediently served for the Australian government at the peak earning moment of my professional journey. Nobody should have right to cease my scholarship money or earned money or achieved money. I personally invested around 45,558 AUD to 10,00,100 AUD to win Australian government RTP stipend scholarship from my child schooling to PhD schooling through the long-term preparation process in my self-funded study centre.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

"Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>

Nobody should cease my dream. Nobody should cause me an artificial brain injury. Nobody should kill me for any personal benefit. This scholarship money should be my fixed deposit money in my Australian bank account for two-three years duration when I have been regularly sacrificing my quality food and quality life-style since July 2022. Nobody should cease my fixed deposit money for two-three years duration against of my compensated salary at RMIT University, Australia. After my second milestone examination, after writing about my life-threatening conspiracy to the Vice Chancellor of RMIT University, after asking my safety support about my life-threatening conspiracy to the Vice Chancellor of RMIT University, I got an 'illegal gift letter' of 'PhD suspension' and 'psychologist recommendation' for one year duration on 6 July 2022. I suspect that the one-year duration 'psychologist recommendation' was also a repeated conspiracy of repeated life-threatening in Bangladesh and/or Australia. PhD suspension and 'psychologist recommendation' were also an official hiding technique of life-threatening conspiracy. These should be the symptom of serious official offence in an official platform in Australian PhD school. But still now I am practicing my PhD research and publication on behalf of RMIT University, government of Australia.

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742977>

Parallely I am convincing and convincing the artificial incidence of life-threatening conspiracy in RMIT PhD school. I am truly attaching my relevant facts for your ethical and legal consideration for the peace of mankind. I like Bangladesh; I like Australia; I do not like any criminal of any government. I got the honour of Bangladesh government; I got the honour of Australian government. But I would like to want my legal rights all over the world. Asking for legal rights should not be considered as crime of a plaintiff. If I invented criminal activities in Australian PhD school, if I briefly reported the criminal activities in Australian PhD school, if I faced crimes and harassment in a PhD school, if I am scholarly convincing and convincing, it should be my professional recognition for the peace of global PhD schooling. May I want recognition of my invention instead of my continuous life-threatening. May I want parallel recognition of Bangladesh

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

government and Australian government. May I seek ethical and financial support from the whole president all over the world to eliminate international criminals. International criminals are a burden to global survival. International criminals are successfully performing against the global peace of human being. May I want the ethical voice of the whole professor community, the whole researcher community, the whole scientist community, the whole student community all over the world. Possibly, everyone would like to see the legal excellence of global peace of humankind all over the world.

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A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2025, designated for Md. Anwar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862986>

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Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>

Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>

Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884624>

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The whole administrative concerns all over the world are being requested and requested to extend their ethical power for the peace of humankind. Let's shout and shout by saying the following words to establish the speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist. "Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world."

At the end of letter, I have also attached my 'income tax e-return' to the Bangladesh government for the assessment year 2024-2025. Evidence of my permanent residence (PR) by birth: Nationality, National ID (Membership ID of Prime minister selection committee and president selection committee of Bangladesh government), Passport and Birth Registration Number: Bangladeshi (by birth), 19862692620993890, EE0444946 (Present)/AF3831770 (previous), 003236; Taxpayer's identification number (TIN) in Bangladesh: 148239262936. Permanent Residence (PR) By Birth: Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia.

I have no money to submit a printed copy of my whole document to the office of 'president' and the office of 'chief advisor'. There are also relevant online links and references for relevant consideration. So, I am submitting the online version for your kind acceptance, kind assessment, and kind consideration on behalf of Bangladesh government, Australian government, and relevant authorities.

The chief governance of Bangladesh and the chief governance of Australia are being requested to take the necessary action for the global excellency in PhD schooling. Therefore, may I seek the following support to establish my legal voice for the peace of humankind, for the peace of PhD schooling all over the world.

- income support and/or salary
- free of cost legal support and/or legal funding
- free of cost safety for the protection against Australian criminal

Your Honour, Please Pardon me

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Best Regards for your excellency for the peace of mankind

7 November 2024

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(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist
PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia.

**Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.**

Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;
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Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

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Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;
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Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>;
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

For showing my honour, for the excellency of PhD schooling and human being all over the world; may I am also forward (randomly sequenced) a copy of this letter for their excellency

The whole incidence is being kept and recorded in online platform for the peace of PhD schooling for the peace of professor community for the peace human being all over the world.

Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist
PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia.
lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist
PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia.
robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au
robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com

Mr. Anthony Albanese, MP, Australian Prime Minister, Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet, The Commonwealth of Australia
Online form

Mr. Jason Clare, MP, Education Minister and/or Secretary of Education Department, The Commonwealth of Australia
contact.centre@education.gov.au

Mr. Donald Trump, President, United States of America
Online form

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Mr. António Guterres, Secretary General, United Nations
Online form

Chairman, University Grant Commission, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd
secretary@ugc.gov.bd
syrawarn@gmail.com
nazmul@ugc.gov.bd
director_research@ugc.gov.bd
ferdousugc@gmail.com

Page | 18

Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia
vc@rmit.edu.au
brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au
ea.vc@rmit.edu.au
jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au
nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au

Justice Syed Refaat Ahmed, Chief Justice, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
contact@dhakatribune.com

Brig Gen Prof. Dr. Engr. Md Lutfor Rahman (Retd), Vice Chancellor, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd
registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Shah-E-Alam, Former Vice Chancellor, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
registrar@smuct.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Niaz Ahmed Khan, Vice Chancellor, University of Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
registrar@du.ac.bd

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Mr. M. Allama Siddiki, High Commissioner of The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh, The Commonwealth of Australia

consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd

Ms. Nardia Simpson, Acting High Commissioner of Australia, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

Ministry of Home affairs, The Commonwealth of Australia
Online form

Foreign Minister and/or Foreign Secretary, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

fs@mofa.gov.bd

dirfso@mofa.gov.bd

ssa@mofa.gov.bd

aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd

dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd

dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd

asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd

Ms. Penny Wong, Foreign Minister and/or Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade, The Commonwealth of Australia

vso@dfat.gov.au

Professor Dr. AK Samanta, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, West Bengal, The Republic of India

ijtaksamanta@gmail.com

ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Abser, Jahangirnagar University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
abserju@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Mohammad Kamrul Ahsan, Vice Chancellor, Jahangirnagar University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrarju@gmail.com

registrar@juniv.edu

Professor Dr. Danmei Sun, Herriot Watt University, United Kingdom
d.sun@hw.ac.uk

Professor Dr. Engr. Saifur Rahman, Daffodil International University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
drsaifur@diu.edu.bd
fukudaiko@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Ayub Nabi, Pro Vice Chancellor, BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
provc@buft.edu.bd

Professor Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
s.islam05@gmail.com
saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Dr. Kamal Uddin Ahmed, Chairman, Human Rights Commission, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
fm@nhrc.org.bd
chairman@nhrc.org.bd
secretary@nhrc.org.bd
liptonbjs@gmail.com

Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia
Online form

Editor, The Australians, The Commonwealth of Australia

Let's shout and shout for a 'criminal free' world rather than 'weapon therapy', a speech of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

letters@theaustralian.com.au

victoria@theaustralian.com.au

wa@theaustralian.com.au

act@theaustralian.com.au

Barrister A.M. Mahbub Uddin Khokon, President, Bangladesh Supreme Court Bar Association, Shahbag, Dhaka-1000.

scba.bd@gmail.com

Mr. Peter Dunning KC, President, Australian Bar Association, The Commonwealth of Australia

dunning@callinanchambers.com.au

contact@austbar.asn.au

media@austbar.asn.au

Advocate Kapil Sibal, President, The Bar Association of India, 93, Lawyers Chambers, Supreme Court of India, New Delhi - 110 001, The Republic of India

info@barindia.in

barindia1959@gmail.com

William R. Bay, President, American Bar Association

service@americanbar.org

The Bar Council of United Kingdom

ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk

press@barcouncil.org.uk

Amnesty International, American Human Rights

info.esiaprobangkok@amnesty.org

contactus@amnesty.org

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

head_te@duet.ac.bd

reg_duet@duet.ac.bd

Page | 22

Professor Dr. Md. Abdullah Al Mamun, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Maulana Bhashani Science and Technology University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@mbstu.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Anwarul Azim Akhand, Vice Chancellor, Maulana Bhashani Science and Technology University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@mbstu.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Mohammad Abdul Jalil, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd

Prof. Mohammad Mashud, Vice Chancellor, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

registrar@kuet.ac.bd

vc@kuet.ac.bd

ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd

Engr. Md. Ashraful Kabir, Chairman, BCMC College of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

bcmccrm@hotmail.com

Prof. Dr. Nitai Chandra Sutradhar, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Green University of Bangladesh, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

chairman@tex.green.edu.bd

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Shorif Uddin, Vice Chancellor, Green University of Bangladesh, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@green.edu.bd

Mr. Tanvir Ahmed Chowdhury, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Daffodil International University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

headte@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd

Professor Dr. M. Lutfar Rahman, Vice Chancellor, Daffodil International University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd

Professor Dr. Md. Mahbubul Haque, Department of Textile Engineering, Daffodil International University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

drhaque@diu.edu.bd

drhaque@alumni.manchester.ac.uk

Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Bangladesh University of Business and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

info@bubt.edu.bd

Prof. Dr. A B M Shawkat Ali, Vice Chancellor, Bangladesh University of Business and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@bubt.edu.bd

Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Zulhash Uddin, Vice Chancellor, Bangladesh University of Textiles, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@butex.edu.bd

registrar@butex.edu.bd

Prof. Md. Abdul Khaleq, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Prime Asia University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

textile@primeasia.edu.bd

Professor Dr. Suvamoy Datta, Vice Chancellor, Prime Asia University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@primeasia.edu.bd

Page | 24

registrar@primeasia.edu.bd

Head (Acting) & Associate Professor, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, Northern University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

faysal.tex@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Anwar Hossain, Vice-Chancellor, Department of Textile Engineering, Northern University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

info@nub.ac.bd

Prof. Yusuf Mahbulul Islam, Vice Chancellor, Department of Textile Engineering, South East University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ymislam@seu.edu.bd

vc@seu.edu.bd

Prof. Engr. Mashud Ahmed, Chairman, Department of Textile Engineering, South Asia University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

mashud.ahmed@seu.edu.bd

registrar@seu.edu.bd

Professor Dr. Arun Kanti Guha, Department of Textile Engineering, South East University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

arun.guha@seu.edu.bd

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Forhad Hossen, Dean, Dyes and Chemical Engineering Department, Bangladesh University of Textiles, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

head@dce.butex.edu.bd

butexdce@gmail.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Professor Dr Abu Borhan Mohammad Badruzzaman, Vice Chancellor, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

kamrul_regbuet@yahoo.com

rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd

saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Bodh Raj Mehta, Vice Chancellor, Indian Institute of Technology, The Republic of India

registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in

brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in

brmehta_p@hotmail.com

Engr. Sukumar Roy, Chairman, KE Technical Textiles Ltd., The Republic of India

sukumarroy@gmail.com

Professor Swapon Kumar Gosh, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India

ijtskg40@gmail.com

Professor Sadhan Chandra Roy, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India

sadhan53@yahoo.co.in

Dr. Andrea Eckersley, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Scott Mayson, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Sean Ryan, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Xin Wang, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

xin.wang@rmit.edu.au

Academic Registrar, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au

Chief Executive Officer, Victoria Legal Aid, The Commonwealth of Australia

Grants@vla.vic.gov.au

Professor Dr. Alice Payne, Dean, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

alice.payne@rmit.edu.au

Professor Dr. Ray Kirby, Dean, School of Engineering, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au

Professor Iain Martin, Vice Chancellor, Deakin University, The Commonwealth of Australia

igmartin@deakin.edu.au

Professor Calum Drummond, RMIT University, The Commonwealth of Australia

calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au

Professor Dr. Md. Abdur Rahman Bhuiyan, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

arahman@duet.ac.bd

British Library of United Kingdom

customer@bl.uk

Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, RMIT University, Australia; Chief defendant of life-threatening conspiracy against Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

rajiv.padhye@rmit.edu.au

Dr. Kamal Hossain, lawyer, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

khossain@citechco.net

Dr. Mustafa Jalal Mohiuddin, President, Bangladesh Medical Association (BMA), Bangladesh

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Engg
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

bma.org.bd@gmail.com

Ms. Natalia Centellas, Secretary General and Group CEO, Australian Medical Association (AMA), Australia

ama@ama.com.au

Engr. Mohammad Reazul Islam (Rezu), President, The Institution of Engineers, Bangladesh (IEB), Dhaka, Bangladesh

iebhq@gmail.com

info@iebbd.org

Director, Nobel Prize Organization

Online form

Ms. Tasmima Hossain, Editor, The Daily Ittefaq, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

ittefaqdigital@gmail.com

ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com

Registrar office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist; Plaintiff of self-life-threatening conspiracy of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist; The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

If Necessary Please Visit the full Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Samanta et al., 2016) (Hossain, 2023c) (Hossain, 2023c) (**Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bi, 2023ch, 2023ci**) (A. Hossain, 2020,

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2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bt, 2023bu, 2023bv; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024v)

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/JMP-7353-2023>

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

To: secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd, press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd, ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd, akmmonirul31@gmail.com, majumderali1950@gmail.com, musfiquldu33@gmail.com, psecy@cao.gov.bd, secretary@cao.gov.bd, seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd, lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd, sultanpmo1974@gmail.com, ddresearch@cao.gov.bd, jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd

Cc: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au, robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au, robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com, fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd, secretary@ugc.gov.bd, syrawarn@gmail.com, nazmul@ugc.gov.bd, director_research@ugc.gov.bd, ferdousugc@gmail.com, vc@rmit.edu.au, brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au, ea.vc@rmit.edu.au, jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au, nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au, contact@dhakatribune.com, vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd, registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd, registrar@smuct.ac.bd, registrar@du.ac.bd, contact.centre@education.gov.au, consular.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, labour.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, commerce.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, mission.canberra@mofa.gov.bd, ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au, consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au, fs@mofa.gov.bd, dirfso@mofa.gov.bd, ssa@mofa.gov.bd, aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd, dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd, dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd, asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd, vso@dfat.gov.au, ijtaksamanta@gmail.com, ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com, abserju@yahoo.com, d.sun@hw.ac.uk, drsaifur@diu.edu.bd, fukudaiko@yahoo.com, provcc@buft.edu.bd, s.islam05@gmail.com, saiful.bstec@cityuniversity.ac.bd, ftm@nhrc.org.bd, chairman@nhrc.org.bd, secretary@nhrc.org.bd, liptonbjs@gmail.com, letters@theaustralian.com.au, victoria@theaustralian.com.au, wa@theaustralian.com.au, act@theaustralian.com.au, u.scba.bd@gmail.com, dunning@callinanchambers.com.au, contact@austbar.asn.au, media@austbar.asn.au, info@barindia.in, barindia1959@gmail.com, service@americanbar.org, ContactUs@BarCouncil.org.uk, press@barcouncil.org.uk, info.esiaprobangkok@amnesty.org, contactus@amnesty.org, head_te@duet.ac.bd, reg_duet@duet.ac.bd, registrar@mbstu.ac.bd, drjalil@te.kuet.ac.bd, registrar@kuet.ac.bd, vc@kuet.ac.bd, ps2vc@kuet.ac.bd, bcmccrm@hotmail.com, chairman@tex.green.edu.bd, vc@green.edu.bd, headte@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd, vc@daffodilvarsity.edu.bd, drhaque@diu.edu.bd, drhaque@alumni.manchester.ac.uk, info@bubt.edu.bd, vc@bubt.edu.bd, vc@butex.edu.bd, registrar@butex.edu.bd, textile@primeasia.edu.bd, vc@primeasia.edu.bd, registrar@primeasia.edu.bd, faysal.tex@gmail.com, info@nub.ac.bd, ymislam@seu.edu.bd, vc@seu.edu.bd, mashud.ahmed@seu.edu.bd, registrar@seu.edu.bd, arun.guha@seu.edu.bd, head@dce.butex.edu.bd, butexdce@gmail.com, kamrul_regbuat@yahoo.com, rakib_ao@regtr.buet.ac.bd, saikatbarua@dce.buet.ac.bd, registrar@admin.iitd.ac.in, brmehta@physics.iitd.ernet.in, brmehta_p@hotmail.com, sukumarroy@gmail.com, ijtskg40@gmail.com, sadhan53@yahoo.co.in, andrea.eckersley@rmit.edu.au, scott.mayson@rmit.edu.au, sean.ryan@rmit.edu.au, xin.wang@rmit.edu.au, academic.registrar@rmit.edu.au, Grants@vla.vic.gov.au, alice.payne@rmit.edu.au, ray.kirby@rmit.edu.au, igmartin@deakin.edu.au, calum.drummond@rmit.edu.au, arahman@duet.ac.bd, customer@bl.uk, rajiv.padhya@rmit.edu.au, khossain@citechco.net, bma.org.bd@gmail.com, ama@ama.com.au, iebhq@gmail.com, info@iebbd.org, ittefaqdigital@gmail.com, ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com, registrarju@gmail.com, registrar@juniv.edu

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

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Date 7 November 2024

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Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin

President

Office of President

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

Office of President, Bangabhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh

secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd

press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd

ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd

akmmoniru131@gmail.com

Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Economist

Chief Advisor

Office of Chief Advisor

The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

State Guest House Jamuna, Dhaka, Bangladesh

majumderali1950@gmail.com

musfiquldu33@gmail.com

psecy@cao.gov.bd

secretary@cao.gov.bd

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd

lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

sultanpmo1974@gmail.com

ddresearch@cao.gov.bd

jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd

May I seek income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Dear President and Chief Advisor,

Your excellency for the peace of mankind

Your honour to ensure legal rights of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour to ensure legal safety of Bangladeshi Citizen

Your honour for the excellency of global leadership

Your honour for keeping a quality relation with the government of Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

I would like to attach a letter (pdf file) for your kind assessment and consideration to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
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Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of
presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the
world]

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ABA Member Service

From:service@americanbar.org

To:Anowar Hossain

Thu, Nov 7 at 10:38 AM

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Education - Contact Centre

From: contact.centre@education.gov.au

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Nov 7 at 10:42 AM

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Australian Government Department of Education
Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

From:contact.centre@education.gov.au

To:Anowar Hossain

Thu, Nov 7 at 10:43 AM

Page | 36

Good afternoon,

Thank you for contacting the Department of Education.

This enquiry falls outside the scope of the Department, as such we are unable to assist.

Please let us know if you require any further assistance or you may contact us on 1300 363 079 to discuss further

Regards,

Josh

Departmental Contact Centre

Australian Government Department of Education

Phone: 1300 363 079 | Email: contact.centre@education.gov.au

[Department of Education](http://www.education.gov.au)

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Yahoo/Sent

Anowar Hossain

From:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To:SFC@finance.gov.au,feedback@finance.gov.au

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Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile
Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law,
Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
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ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation,
Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Thu, Nov 7 at 11:47 AM

Dear officer,

I would like to forward a cc letter to the honour of Minister of Home affairs. Accordingly, I have attached a pdf file to the office of home affairs.

Page | 37

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

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Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

[SEC=OFFICIAL] Automatic reply: Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel...

Yahoo/Inbox

SFC

From: sfc@finance.gov.au

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Nov 7 at 11:50 AM

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

Thank you for your email to the Department of Finance (Finance) Discretionary Payments team.

Act of Grace (AoG) and Waiver of Debt (WoD) applications:

Page | 40

- General information and application forms can be found here: [Application process for act of grace or waiver of debt | Department of Finance](#)

Please be advised that the act of grace and waiver of debt power is discretionary. This means there is no situation which creates an automatic entitlement to either mechanism.

CDDA Scheme

- General information in relation to the Scheme for Compensation for Detriment caused by Defective Administration can be found here: [CDDA Scheme | Department of Finance](#)

Application Process:

- Once you have submitted your application for AoG or WoD, it will be registered in our database. You may be contacted to provide additional information.
- Finance will then contact the relevant Commonwealth agency, to which your request relates, and seek a submission. Once the submission is received, it will be shared with you for comment as part of the procedural fairness process.
- Following the information gathering stage, a decision brief will be prepared for the consideration of the delegate.

Important to note:

- **Sensitive material:** Please indicate clearly in your correspondence if your application contains highly sensitive or potentially triggering content, including any photographs or video material.
- **Processing timeframes:** Each step in the Act of Grace or Waiver of Debt process can take considerable time and we are not able to provide estimates on when decisions will be finalised and provided to you.

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker, literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

- **Non-Corporate Commonwealth Entity (NCE) Actions:** Waivers are generally only provided for situations arising from actions of Non-Corporate Commonwealth Entities (NCEs). A list of NCEs is available here: [Non-corporate Commonwealth entity \(NCE\)](#)
- **Tax File Numbers:** You are not required to supply your Tax File Number to Commonwealth agencies, unless asked to do so. Providing this number can breach your privacy, so please do not include it in your correspondence or application.
- **Additional information:** If you have additional information, updates or supporting documentation to provide in relation to your matter, you can do so at any time by sending an email to sfc@finance.gov.au.
- **Information on HELP debt management** is available at: [HECS-HELP - Study Assist, Australian Government](#).
- **Hardship:** HELP repayments only begin when your income exceeds the [compulsory repayment threshold](#) (adjusted annually).
- **Indexation:** HELP debts are not charged interest; however, the [ATO applies annual indexation](#) (1 June every year) to maintain debt value. The government does not currently waive indexation.
- **Voluntary Payments:** Voluntary repayments can be made to the ATO any time during a financial year. Processing takes up to 4 days. To avoid additional indexation, ensure payments are received by the ATO before 1 June, please see [ATO website](#) for details. Late payments will not be considered for indexation waivers.

We are committed to treating you with courtesy and respect and expect the same in return. We will not tolerate inappropriate, aggressive, or abusive behaviour or language.

For details of free support services please see: [Find Support | National Mental Health Commission](#).

Kind Regards

Discretionary Payments Team

Procurement and Discretionary Payments Branch

Department of Finance

T: 1800 227 572

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

E: sfc@finance.gov.au

AHRC Make a Complaint Form

Yahoo/Inbox

Page | 42

Australian Human Rights Commission

From: noreply@humanrights.gov.au

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Thu, Nov 7 at 11:59 AM

Complaint

- **Your complaint has been sent!**

Thank you for submitting the complaint form to the Australian Human Rights Commission (the Commission).

If you do not receive contact from the Commission within the next 7 days, please contact the Commission on 1300 656 419 (Monday to Friday 10.00am to 4.00pm Sydney time) or by email at infoservice@humanrights.gov.au to confirm receipt.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Minister Correspondence Reference: MC24-032830

Yahoo/Inbox

From: noreply@homeaffairs.gov.au

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Mon, Nov 11 at 11:41 AM

Thank you for contacting the Minister.

The Minister appreciates hearing your views. Your correspondence will be noted by the Department of Home Affairs and, in some cases, the Department may be asked to respond on the Minister's behalf.

Your request was successfully submitted on 11/11/2024 at 04:41:17 and your reference number is MC24-032830.

If you have concerns about criminal activity in your local community, contact your local police on 131 444 or Crime Stoppers on 1800 333 000.

If you wish to report suspicious activity, you can contact the National Security Hotline in the following ways:

Call: 1800 1234 00

From outside Australia: (+61) 1300 1234 01

Email: hotline@nationalecurity.gov.au

SMS: 0429 771 822

TTY: 1800 234 889

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

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 Phone: 01788396164
 NID:
 To: MR. MOHAMMED SHAHABUDDIN
 Address: PRESIDENT BANGABHABAN, DHAKA
 Phone: 00

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Service Type: General
 From: ANOWER
 Address: TANGAIL
 Phone: 01788396164
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 To: NOBEL WIRRRER PROF, DR MOHAMMAD YOUNS
 Address: JAMUNA STATE GUEST HOUSE , 30 HARA ROAD , DHAKA
 Phone: 00

CASH Ref:

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 Condition Amount with VD Charge : 0
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

To
 ✓ Secretary

Dear Mr. Md. Jahim Uddin,
 I would like to seek an appointment.
 I forwarded few letters to your office since 2022. I sent cc e-mail to your office. I physically met your office. I also physically met your office on 4 February 2025.

Thank you.
 09.02.2025
 Md. Anowar Hossain

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Textile Engineering (Dyeing & Processing)
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International Consultant
 (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, R&D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, PhD Researcher, Law, Criminology, Textile, Chemical & Leatherware industry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime, Criminology & Reporting, Quality in Higher Education); Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammad Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404986>

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My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Dear President,

I would like to seek an appointment. I forwarded a hard copy letter around two months ago. I physically met your office on 4 February 2025.

Thank You

Anowar
04-02-2025

Md. Anowar Hossain

R. K. ROBIQUE
02/02/25

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist
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Mr. Antonio Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations
Requesting a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>

Mr. Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia
Seeking legal support for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18140.19899>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
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 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Dear chief Advisor,

I would like to seek an appointment. A hard copy letters forwarded around two month ago.

Thank You

04.02.2025

Md. Anwar Hossain

International Consultant
 (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, R&D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, PhD Researcher, Law, Criminology, Textile Defence Law/Name issues, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime analysis & Reporting, Quality in Higher Education) Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Textile Engineering (Dyeing & Processing) Textile Engineering (R&D) in Textile Engineering (Dyeing & Processing) PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration) PhD Research ID: 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

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 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTEch, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTEch, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 November 2024; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
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<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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**Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist
PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
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School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of
Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing,
Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in
Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research
Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile
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Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer;
Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet

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Dear Professor Dr. Engr. Hossain

Thank you for getting in touch with the Prime Minister.

Looking at the issues you have raised, I would recommend the Department of Education would be best placed to respond to you.

To assist with that, we have referred your correspondence to the Department of Education for their consideration.

Please keep in mind that your correspondence might need input from multiple government departments or agencies and this could take time to compile for you.

You can contact the Department of Education regarding the progress of your correspondence by visiting their contact us web page.

On behalf of the Prime Minister, thank you again for getting in touch.

Yours sincerely

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads 'Megan'.

Megan
Senior Adviser
Ministerial Correspondence Unit
Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet

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All items of correspondence are read and carefully considered, however not all items will receive a response.

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Thank you for your correspondence to the Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister. The Prime Minister appreciates you taking the time to write to him.

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জাতীয় রাজস্ব বোর্ড
(আয়কর অফিস)

আয়কর রিটার্ন প্রাপ্তি স্বীকার পত্র/প্রত্যয়ন পত্র

করবর্ষ: ২০২৪-২০২৫

করদাতার নাম: Md. Anowar Hossain

জাতীয় পরিচয়পত্র নম্বর/পাসপোর্ট নম্বর: ১৯৮৬২৬৯২৬২০৯৯৩৮৯০

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কর অঞ্চল: 08, Dhaka

মোট আয়: ০ টাকা

মোট পরিশোধিত কর: ০ টাকা

রিটার্ন রেজিস্টারের ক্রমিক নম্বর	৮৪৮৬৪৩৩৯৫৯
রিটার্ন রেজিস্টারের ভল্যুম নম্বর	
রিটার্ন দাখিলের তারিখ	২৯/১০/২০২৪

অফিসের সিলমোহর

রিটার্ন গ্রহণকারী কর্মকর্তার স্বাক্ষর ও সিল

সিস্টেম জেনারেটেড ডকুমেন্ট। স্বাক্ষরের প্রয়োজন নেই।